

Kinetics of Oxidation of Malonic and Malic Acids by Cerium(VI)

R. K. PRASAD and S. N. TRIPATHY

Post-graduate Department of Chemistry, Bihar University, L. S. College, Muzaffarpur-842 001.

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The kinetics of oxidation of malonic and malic acids by Ce(IV) has been investigated in H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and CH_3COOH acids. The influence of H^+ on the rate of the reactions at constant ionic strength has been carefully examined. Ce(III) sulphate has been found to significantly retard the reaction. A mechanism of the oxidations consistent with these observations has been proposed.

THE kinetics of oxidation of malonic and malic acids by Ce(IV) have been partly reported earlier¹⁻⁶. The mechanism suggested involves a rapid formation of Ce(IV)-substrate complex followed by its slow decomposition to give free radicals. Richardson⁶, however, does not find out evidences for such complexes. In view of the role played by these reactions in the Belousov-Zhabotinskii oscillating reaction systems and the effect of various mineral acids produced on it, we proposed to investigate the stoichiometry and kinetics of these reactions in H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and CH_3COOH .

Experimental

Material and Methods: $Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (Riedel, G. R.), Malic acid (Riedel, G. R.), Malonic acid (L. R., Sigma), Ferrous ammonium sulphate (G. R., E. Merck), Ceric ammonium sulphate (L. R., S. Merck), Ferroin (E. Merck) were used. For kinetics and stoichiometric determinations Ce(IV) solutions were prepared by dissolving $Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ crystals in $N H_2SO_4$. Ceric sulphate could not be dissolved in aqueous H_3PO_4 or even $H_2SO_4 + H_3PO_4$ mixture unless the $[H_2SO_4] \approx 6N$. Therefore, to see the effect of H_3PO_4 on the rate the Ce(IV) solutions were prepared in $6N H_2SO_4 + x N H_3PO_4$ mixture where x varied from 0 to 6N (Table 4). Concentrations mentioned in the table are the ultimate concentrations on mixing the reactants.

For following the rate of reactions, 25 ml of substrate and oxidant were mixed in a thermostat (± 0.05). An aliquot of the reaction mixture at an equal interval of time was quenched in slight excess of standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution and back titrated by standard ceric ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator. In presence of high concentration of SO_4^{2-} for maintaining constant μ (Table 3) and also of H_3PO_4 (Table 4) the rates of reactions in case of malic acid could be conveniently followed at 40° instead of 30° .

Stoichiometry :

Stoichiometries of these reactions depend on the period of storage of reaction mixtures. On prolonged storage 6 and 8.5 moles of Ce(IV) were found to be consumed per mole of malonic and malic acid respectively in the range of H_2SO_4 used. Formic acid was identified in the product by chromotropic acid test¹⁰. This corresponds to the following equations

Acetic acid does not affect the stoichiometry but phosphoric acid drastically alters it, more so in the case of malic acid.

Results and Discussion

Linearity of the plots of $\log \frac{[Ce(IV)]_0}{[Ce(IV)]_t}$ versus

t (Fig. 1) where subscripts indicate time, showed the reactions to be of first order with respect to Ce(IV). (pseudo first order rate constant k_1 given in Table 1). In the case of malonic acid slight deviation of the point of convergence from origin may be an indication of a period of induction. Since on doubling the $[S]_0$ (S=substrate) at constant $[H^+]_0$, k_1 is almost doubled and the plot of $\log k_1 \sim \log [S]$ yield a straight line with slope $\approx +1$ (Fig. 2) the order with respect to substrate is also one.

The plots of $k_1^{-1} \sim S^{-1}$ are straight lines passing almost through origin (Fig. 3). This suggests that

Fig. 1. (A, B, C, D & A', B', C', D' refer to the various concentrations of substrate as given in Table 1)

Fig. 2.

Temperature 30°C			Temperature 25°C		
[m.a.] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ³	k ₁ /[m.a.]	[M.A.] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ³	k ₁ /[M.A.]
10	7.926	0.7926	10	5.654	0.565
6.66	5.817	0.8726	6.66	4.040	0.606
5.00	4.318	0.8630	5.00	2.900	0.580
4.00	3.472	0.8683	4.00	2.360	0.590

* Values of k₁ in this and other tables are in sec⁻¹.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF H₂SO₄

[H ₂ SO ₄]	[Ce(IV)]=5 × 10 ⁻³ M	
	[m.a.] = 1 × 10 ⁻³ M Temp. = 30°C	[M.A.] = 1 × 10 ⁻³ M Temp. = 25°C
0.5	k ₁ × 10 ³ = 7.926	k ₁ × 10 ³ = 5.654
1.0	2.4179	4.390
2.5	0.7807	3.918
3.0	0.5796	2.671

m.a. = malic acid, M.A. = malonic acid.

Fig. 3.

the slow step of the reaction is not preceded by any stable complex formation.

Effect of [H⁺] on the rate :

The plot of log k₁ ~ log [H⁺] at constant ionic strength and constant [S]₀ yield a curve with slope changing through the limiting values of -1 → 0 → +1 → +2 with increasing [H⁺] (Table 3, Fig. 4). This indicates a complex rate equation⁷ of the type

$$k = \frac{k_1}{[S]} = f[H^+] = a[H^+]^{-1} + b + c[H^+] + d[H^+]^2$$

where k is bimolecular rate constant. This equation cannot be rearranged into a linear form but plots of k₁/[S] ~ [H⁺]⁻¹ at low [H⁺] should be linear. Values of k₁/[S] plotted against [H⁺]⁻¹ in the [H⁺] range 0.25M to 1 M actually yield straight lines (Fig. 5). At higher [H⁺] there is distinct departure from linearity (Fig. 6).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[H^+]$ AT CONSTANT $\mu=3.75^*$

$[H^+]M$	$[Ce(IV)]=5 \times 10^{-3}M$	
	$[m.a.] = 1 \times 10^{-2}M$ Temp. = 40°C	$[M.A.] = 1 \times 10^{-2}M$ Temp. = 25°C
0.25	$k_1 \times 10^4$ 26.19	$k_1 \times 10^5$ 2.3172
0.5	11.602	1.515
1.0	5.575	1.388
1.5	5.354	1.640
2.0	8.076	2.321
2.5	12.193	3.918

* Contribution by H_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 only calculated.

Fig. 4.

This behaviour can be understood in terms of the Hardwick and Robertson's equilibrium data⁹ involving various Ce(IV) species in H_2SO_4 wherein

$$[Ce(IV)]_T = [Ce^{4+}] + [CeSO_4^{3+}] + [Ce(SO_4)_2] + [Ce(SO_4)_3^{--}] \dots (1)$$

(T stands for total concentration). On the basis of these data $[Ce(IV)]_T \approx [Ce(SO_4)_3^{--}]$ in the range of acid concentration used. Assuming at high $[H^+]$ both $CeSO_4^{3+}$ and $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and at low $[H^+]$ the hydrolysed product⁹ of $Ce(SO_4)_3^{--}$ are the reactive species,

$$-\frac{d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} = [S] \{ k'[Ce(SO_4)_3OH^{---}] + k''[Ce(SO_4)_3^{--}] + k'''[Ce(SO_4)_2] + k''''[Ce(SO_4)^{3+}] \}$$

Fig. 5.

Fig. 6.

$$= [S] \left\{ \frac{k'K_4}{[H^+]} + k'' + \frac{k'''[H^+]}{K_2[HSO_4^-]} + \frac{k''''[H^+]^2}{K_2K_3[HSO_4^-]^2} \right\} \times [Ce(IV)]_T$$

where $K_1 (= 3500)$, $K_2 (= 200)$ and $K_3 (= 20)$ are the equilibrium constant data of Hardwick and Robertson⁹, $K_4 (= ?)$ is the constant for the equi-

rium(2) ; and k' , k'' , k''' and k'''' are the individual rate constants.

At constant ionic strength and hence at constant HSO_4^- , the above equation may be reduced to the form,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \left\{ a[\text{H}^+]^{-1} + b + c[\text{H}^+] + d[\text{H}^+]^2 \right\} [\text{S}][\text{Ce(IV)}]_t$$

where $a = k' K_4$; $b = k''$; $c = \frac{k'''}{K_3[\text{HSO}_4^-]}$ and

$d = \frac{k''''}{K_2 K_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2}$ and the expression in the middle bracket is equal to $k_1/[\text{S}]$.

Acetic acid tends to increase the rate though the effect is not prominent. Phosphoric acid, on the other hand, has a pronounced retarding effect (Table 4). This is due to strong complexation of the reactive Ce(IV) species with phosphate ions and consequent lowering of the redox potential of Ce(IV)/Ce(III) couple.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF H_3PO_4

$[\text{Ce(IV)}] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3N$
 $[\text{m.a.}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$ $[\text{M.A.}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$
 Temp. = 40°C 25°C

$[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4] N$	$k_2 \times 10^4$	$k_1 \times 10^3$
0	7.45	2.671
0.25	5.648	2.598
0.5	4.209	1.885
1.0	2.825	1.196
2.0	1.599	0.7001
3.0	0.966	0.2738

Like neutral sulphates^{1,2,5} sodium acetate was also found to slightly retard the rate. When $[\text{NaOAc}]$ changes from 0 to $20 \times 10^{-2} M$ the rate constant changes from 7.926×10^{-3} to 7.79×10^{-3} in case of malic acid and 2.886×10^{-3} to 2.409×10^{-3} in case of malonic acid.

That the reaction involves a reversible formation of free radicals in the initial step has been proved by (i) the retarding effect of Ce(III) ion, when Ce(III) changes from 0 to 0.05M the rate constant k_1 changes from 5.654×10^{-3} to 3.850×10^{-3} in case of malonic acid and 7.926×10^{-3} to 6.834×10^{-3} in case of malic acid; (ii) acceleratory effect of benzoyl peroxide (a convenient source of free radical, traces of benzoyl peroxide increase the value of k_1 from 7.926×10^{-3} to 9.1625×10^{-3} in malic acid and from 5.654×10^{-3} to 5.925×10^{-3} in malonic acid) on the rates of the reactions and (iii) the polymerisation of acrylonitrile, and acrylamide in nitrogen atmosphere.

Effect of Temperature :

From the effect of temperature and the corresponding Arrhenius plots the values of the activation parameters were found as follows :

Activation Parameters	MALIC ACID		MALONIC ACID	
	With Acetic Acid	Without Acetic Acid	With Acetic Acid	Without Acetic Acid
E_a	22.4 K.Cal	21.01 K.Cal	10.21 K.Cal	10.082 K.Cal
A	$3.37 \times 10^{13} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$5.27 \times 10^{13} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$1.45 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$1.03 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
S	3.38 E.U.	-0.287 E.U.	-32.79 E.U.	-85.47 E.U.

The values of activation energy are in fair agreement with Bakore³ and Bhagwat⁵.

Mechanisms :

On the basis of these observations it is supposed that the reactive forms of Ce(IV) abstract an electron from the substrate in the initial step leading to the reversible formation of a free radical.

where R^* = free radical and P_1 is a two electron intermediate oxidation product of the substrate (S).

Assuming the subsequent steps to be very fast and using the steady state approximation for the free radical the following rate equation may be derived

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{2 k_2 k_3 [\text{S}][\text{Ce(IV)}]^2}{k_{-2}[\text{Ce(III)}] + k_3[\text{Ce(IV)}]} f([\text{H}^+])$$

and k_2 , k_{-2} and k_3 represent the microscopic rate constant of individual steps of (i) and (ii).

It is clear that in the beginning when Ce(III) is totally absent the reaction is first order with respect to both oxidant and substrate. It also explains the inhibitory effect of Ce(III).

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